

ISSUES OF DEVELOPMENT OF INVESTMENT ATTRACTIVENESS OF UZBEKISTAN AS A PRODUCT-PRODUCING COUNTRY

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Abstract: Foreign direct investment is one of the most important issues in the country's economic policy. In order to attract foreign investors, it is important to increase the attractiveness of the country's image, to positively shape its image in the international arena. This article examines the relationship between foreign investment and the country's image, and analyzes the relationship between these two concepts and how they affect Uzbekistan's economic and investment policy.

Key words: Foreign investments, country image, country of origin, internal image, external image, public relations, made in UZB.

The socio-economic progress of the country, the achievement of stable economic growth, the increase in the income of the population, and the improvement of living conditions in most cases depend on the size and composition of investment funds attracted to various sectors and sectors of the national economy. Therefore, it is natural that every country pays special attention to the creation of an attractive environment for attracting investment funds to the national economy, which is the priority direction of the socio-economic development strategy. Based on this, in order to develop the country's economy and attract more foreign investment, it is an urgent issue to form and promote a true and reliable image of the country. For this, first of all, it is very important for each country to form its internal and external image. The internal image of the country is the image created by the citizens. The external image is the image that is created based on what other people say about our country. We can say that "lifestyle" is considered as a means of shaping the country's reputation, and every city should have future plans that attract residents to their places. Every city in any country is a creator of the country's image. If a city has a good reputation, it affects the image of the country. Country image is defined as the sum of all descriptive, inferential and informational beliefs about a particular country. The image of the territory is a sum of all emotional and aesthetic qualities, such as the experience, beliefs, ideas, memories and impressions of a person about the place known to him. In this definition, it is clear that individuals form an image based on their personal information base. Export, foreign direct investment and tourism sectors can be cited as examples of various methods of designing a nation's national brand. A common social image of a place can be created because individual images are constantly socialized using common languages, symbols, and experiences. The image of some nations, no matter how right or wrong it is, develops in a very complex process of communication, which includes various sources of information. The process begins with one's early life experiences; at school; in children's books, fairy tales and other leisure literature; theater and others, as well as the interaction of relatives, acquaintances and friends. But "international programs, radio and television broadcasts of newspapers and magazines, cultural exchange programs, sports, books, news services, etc. are the most powerful image-forming tools. From this point of view, "the goals of promotional activities can be summarized as follows:

- Forming an opinion among the target audience who has no idea about the topic;

- Developing or improving the image;
- Opposing a negative image and changing it to a positive image” [1]

“In an increasingly complex and interconnected world, not only companies, but also countries are competing at all levels”. [2] S. Anholt notes that “globalization is turning the world into a giant supermarket”. [3] All over the world, countries are competing to promote exports, attract tourism, foreign investment and immigration.

Uzbek scientist A. J. Siddikov writes in his scientific work about investments: “in most cases, the country's socio-economic development, sustainable economic growth, increase in population income, and improvement of living conditions are attracted to various sectors and branches of the national economy and it depends on the size and composition of funds. Therefore, it is inevitable that the priority direction of the socio-economic development strategy of each country should be focused on creating an attractive environment for attracting investment funds to the national economy”. [4] Foreign investors' investment in the national economy largely depends not only on the rating of enterprises or the results of economic activity, but also on the geopolitical location of the country and the internal and external policies of the state. Investors choose the most stable countries for capital investment. Therefore, all countries of the world try to reduce investment risk as much as possible.

There are many businessmen in Uzbekistan who bring foreign investment and get good results. One of them is the investment of 10.2 million dollars by Brilliant Silk LLC in Bukhara with Singapore's Kinzhou Natural Fildo Biotechnology, which created 1,500 jobs thanks to the Chinese-style cocoon cultivation and processing project. Also, “Knauf Gypsum Bukhara” LLC in Kogon district specialized in the production of 120,000 tons of products per year due to the investment of 36.3 million dollars from the German company “Knauf Group”.

At the same time, the mass media in Uzbekistan are trying to spread information to the whole world about the great achievements of the Republic. However, it would be appropriate to increase the efficiency of the existing information potential, to strengthen the mechanisms that strengthen the country's image in the world media space, and to generalize the work in this regard. In this sense, according to P. Zhukova, “in modern society, there is always a need to objectively coordinate the behavior of subjects in the field of defense, security and image formation. In our opinion, it should be a component of the system of democratic control of the defense and security sectors in the country.” [5]

In this definition, one of the important functions of relations with the international public - the function of ensuring the national security of the country - is specifically mentioned. However, international public relations perform many tasks. Because of this, its comprehensive development remains an important issue. Today, Uzbekistan has firmly established its position of building a free civil society based on the principles of democracy. In this way, the phenomenon of public relations has the importance of uniting our entire nation around a single goal. It is through the means of information that we can involve every citizen, the whole nation, in the processes in our country.

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